

Deliverable D3.6

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1 Executive summary

This document updates the previous report (D3.3) on the requirements for the use of structural biology data expressed by other research infrastructures (RIs) not directly operating in the field of structural biology. A detailed analysis of current and emerging usage of structural biology data in the context of different biomedical RI's was reported by West-Life partners as Deliverable 3.5; the latter addressed the implementation and development of approaches to bridge structural information and the biomedical information provided by the biomedical RIs. Consequently, in this report we focus mainly on possible synergistic actions involving West-Life and biomedical RI's aimed at enhancing the visibility and the usage of their services (physical and electronic) by an extended basis of users from the domain of the Life Sciences.

2 Detailed report on the deliverable

2.1 Interaction with the Biomedical RIs

We integrate the information gathered at the round table (RT) event that the West-Life and iNEXT projects co-organized in Brno, Czech Republic, on May 24th, 2017 in collaboration with Instruct (<https://www.structuralbiology.eu/content/bringing-together-the-bio-medical-scientific-communities-the-role-of-research-infrastructures>) with a second follow-up RT on the occasion of the annual meeting of the CORBEL project (<http://www.corbel-project.eu/home.html>). This event took place in Amsterdam, The Netherlands on October 26th, 2017. The RT was entitled "Visibility, usage and impact of research infrastructures - follow up of the Brno Round Table" and was organized as a luncheon meeting and focused on the (re)evaluation of the main items outlined and the actions already initiated following the round table event that took place in Brno on May 2017 (described in detail in Deliverable 3.2).

The initial discussion focused on the following points, which then were agreed as action items in the first RT:

- Creation of a database of all the services of the BMS RIs as a starting point for building a common web site of BMS RIs

- Ask MERIL-2, RISCAPE, RICH 2020 to improve the visibility of BMS RIs – e.g. by providing a dedicated space
- Preparation of a common document for EC, and later for other funding bodies, advocating the implementation of a top-down approach to actively encourage applicants to use RI services
- Create an interface with the European Open Science Cloud as well as the EOOSC Pilot to implement a preferential channel of communication with RIs

In addition to the points mentioned above, the role of electronic infrastructures and Virtual Research Environments (VREs), such as West-Life, to enhance the visibility of physical RIs has been discussed.

Regarding the first point, the CORBEL catalogue is now live at <http://www.corbel-project.eu/services.html> to make it suitable for use in different contexts (e.g., from searching partners for applications to calls to guiding potential new users to identify infrastructures offering services of interest).

Concerning the second point, preliminary contacts with representatives of the MERIL-2 and RICH 2020 projects have been established and the discussion on possible solutions for promoting/increasing visibility of BMS RIs in their websites is ongoing.

Extensive discussions related to the interaction of BMS RIs with the European Open Science Cloud (EOOSC) took place within the context of developing an application to the H2020 call INFRAEOOSC-04-2018 “Connecting ESFRI infrastructures through Cluster projects”; they are also summarized in the next section. The concept of the aforementioned application was initially designed in the context of the CORBEL partnership. Eventually the consortium of the new application involved 63 organizations associated with thirteen biomedical RIs (BBMRI, EATRIS, ECRIN, ELIXIR, EMBRC, EMPHASIS, ERINHA, EuBI, EU-OPENSOURCE, INFRAFRONTIER, INSTRUMENT, ISBE, MIRRI).

2.2 Response from the biomedical RIs

The following participated in the second RT:

1. Serena Battaglia (ECRIN)
2. Susan Daenke (INSTRUCT)

3. Sven Fahrner (EMPHASIS)
4. Antje Keppler (EuroBioImaging)
5. Frauke Leitner (Euro-BioImaging)
6. Giovanni Migliaccio (EATRIS)
7. Francesca Morelli (West-Life)
8. Antonio Rosato (West-Life)
9. Edoardo Saccenti (ISBE)
10. Friederike Schmidt-Tremmel (ELIXIR)

All the participants agreed on the need for BMS RIs to enhance their visibilities through targeted actions supporting an interdisciplinary approach to improving awareness of RI services throughout the entire domain the Life Sciences. This need regards both electronic (e.g. web-based) services and provision of access to physical facilities, technologies and expertise. Overall, services can simply be consultation, access to experts, access to data and biological samples, access to facilities (e.g. cryo-EM microscopes, synchrotrons, NMR spectrometers) plus support from technicians, as well as use of data processing and analysis tools (on-premises or, more commonly, remotely via web interfaces), provision of software for data integration.

In this sense, it would be highly desirable to promote the dissemination of infrastructure services in a cross-disciplinary manner to the whole scientific community and especially to graduate students and postdocs, possibly via personal interactions (e.g., University career days). For this, initiatives such as CORBEL should foster the preparation of promotional material to allow publicity of all BMS RIs already at the level / by the staff of a single RI node. User interviews can be an important part of this approach (<http://www.corbel-project.eu/success-stories.html>). West-Life could provide a perspective from users benefiting of data access and automated data analysis, to complement and better exploit the services provided by experimental facilities.

As detailed better in D3.5, the first open call for projects by CORBEL indicated that structural biology data are relevant within the two tracks of “Predictive system pharmacology for safer drugs and chemical products” and “Structure function analysis of large macromolecules”, but also in so-called cross-Access tracks, partnering especially with Euro-BioImaging and EU-Openscreen. Nevertheless, there are several other biomedical RIs that are strongly linked to

Instruct-ERIC and structural biology data, including ELIXIR, INFRAFRONTIER, EATRIS, BBMRI and ISBE. Thus the cross-disciplinary approach advocated in the preceding paragraphs is indeed rooted in the users' requirements, as demonstrated by their applications to the CORBEL call. Seamless data exchange based on cloud storage and computing is a crucial requirement to enable truly interdisciplinary approaches.

In the context of the INFRAEOSC-04-2018 application, it has been made explicit that modern biology rests on the generation, sharing and integrated analysis of digital data. A rational molecular understanding of biological systems relies on the study of the molecular composition of life systematically and at all its different scales: from molecules at subatomic resolution up to ecosystems. Creation of knowledge happens by connecting the very large amounts of digital life science data. Today, big life science datasets extend from nucleic acid sequences (genomics) to structural and imaging technologies that generate comprehensive molecular descriptions of the core processes of life. In the environmental and agricultural sciences these molecular descriptions need to be linked to data on environment, yields and climate; in medicine to diagnosis, treatment outcomes and social data. As life-science datasets grow larger and multidimensional, the complexity of the tools and the computational intensity required to process and analyze this data frequently outgrows the capabilities of individual research teams. Providing compute resources from a large shared pool, giving open access to data by cloud computation technologies and making integrated systems for data analysis available via web interfaces empowers researchers regardless of their location and of the size of their institution. This is exactly the model designed by the West-Life VRE. Indeed, a crucial need for current research in the life sciences is the availability of dedicated computational tools in the form of cloud-/grid-based workflows to analyze large quantities of data in an integrated and multi-scale (time and/or spatial) manner. Data sharing and re-use via the cloud will fuel new ground-breaking discoveries. Moreover, re-use and re-analysis ensures the quality and reproducibility of the results of research in structural biology and beyond. In this frame, there is now a unique opportunity to ensure that biomedical research data conforms to the FAIR principles. This is also made possible by the use of large scale RIs such as Instruct-ERIC, which can support in collaboration with electronic infrastructures the proper preparation of data and metadata. FAIR means that data and virtual services built on them are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable for researchers across many scientific disciplines and national boundaries. Effective data preservation and open access for immediate and future sharing and

re-use are a fundamental component of reproducible and innovative scientific research. Broad access to FAIR structural data through the EOSC thanks to the support by data experts at the RIs and within companion electronic infrastructures will open unprecedented opportunities to researchers in all fields of the biomedical sciences. In addition to the above considerations, we expect that this project, if funded, will create a channel by which users (i.e. individual research teams) from different communities will be to provide direct input regarding the computational aspects of the integration of structural data with the research data of their own community. Indeed, within the eight pilot “Demonstrators” already planned within the project, two explicitly involve the use of structural biology data within multi-disciplinary pipelines for data analysis.

2.3 Overall conclusions

There is a broad and general consensus, as outlined also in other documents produced by the West-Life project, that Structural Biology data, especially 3D coordinate data, are of relevance to basically all RI's in biomedical research. Nevertheless, the integration of structural data with the data produced by other communities in the life sciences must be pursued further. In this sense, the role of electronic infrastructures and Virtual Research Environments such as West-Life is crucial. With the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) initiative getting off the ground, the interaction between physical and electronic infrastructures, especially in the context of ESFRI infrastructures, will have an essential role to ensure that the data produced by RI users are effectively available to and can be re-used by the entire scientific community. To fulfil this overall goal, there are significant technical aspects regarding data management that require a dedicated effort by data experts. Making data available in a FAIR manner is not sufficient, the community must have access to appropriate workflows for data re-analysis and interpretation. This will facilitate re-use of structural data beyond the community of structural biologists. To facilitate this, it would be very useful to collect and organize currently available analysis pipelines. This is in line with the overall strategy being implemented within the support activities of West-Life, whose aims include making the provision and use of advanced computational tools in integrated structural biology easier for end-users.

Enhancing the visibility and fostering usage of RI's, both physical and electronic, remains a high priority of all the stakeholders in the field. This is even more true in the context of the EOSC, because RIs are in the best position to guarantee the quality of data that will be

available to the community. In other words, high-quality data provision to the scientific community via EOSC is a clear mandate of large RIs, particularly ESFRIs. This role of RIs must be disseminated to all biomedical researchers, in a cross disciplinary manner, so that researchers will aim to access the appropriate RIs or to use RI data especially when in activities that go beyond the borders of their own scientific subdomain. Therefore, RIs are teaming up both to promote the dissemination of infrastructure services and to encourage national and European funders to implement mechanisms fostering usage of RIs by funded projects.

We will take the opportunity of the next Annual Meeting of CORBEL (October 2018) to assess the progress made with respect to the various items outlined in this document.